

Interoperability Stories Report

January 2025

ELIXIR

Project Title:	<i>2022 EIP Task 1</i>
Deliverable title:	<i>Final report of completed interoperability stories, technical solutions, dissemination and impact to EIP knowledge hub</i>
Deliverable number:	<i>D1.1</i>
Partner(s) contributing to this deliverable:	<i>NO, BE, NL, GR, IT, UK, EMBL-EBI</i>
Report Author(s):	<i>Tony Burdett, Fabio Liberante</i>

Executive Summary	1
Details of the Deliverable	2
Interoperability Stories - Overview and Technical Solutions	2
Intrinsically Disordered Protein Community Interoperability Showcase: Exploiting Bioschemas Markup	3
Plant Sciences Community Showcase	3
Rare Disease Community Interoperability Showcase: examples from EJP RD	3
Mapping the DCAT-based EJP RD Metadata Model to Bioschemas for improved interoperability	4
User journeys as means of effectively demonstrating value and engaging stakeholders	4
Galaxy: a story about interoperability	4
FAIRtracks and Omnipy - FAIRtracks interoperability story	4
Single Cell Omics Community Interoperability Showcase	5
Metabolomics Community & Interoperability Platform - On which subjects could they collaborate?	5
Lessons Learned	5
Dangers to Avoid	6
Dissemination and Impact	7
Adjustments Made	8

Executive Summary

From June 2022 until December 2023, the ELIXIR Interoperability Platform worked with seven different ELIXIR Communities to compile and present nine distinct interoperability stories. The diverse set of stories showcased case studies and use cases for enhanced data reuse across the ELIXIR network, and explored the tools, processes, workflows, databases and approaches the different communities took to achieve impact through interoperable data sharing. This report recaps the key messages from those interoperability stories, identifies some common themes and technical solutions, and provides a synopsis of the main lessons learned from these stories.

Details of the Deliverable

Plan of work:

Solicit and consolidate a set of stories across ELIXIR communities, encompassing data and analysis aspects

Define requirements for interoperability stories and communicate these into task 1.2

Gather, evaluate suitability, and provide feedback on technical solutions from task 1.2

Align and disseminate interoperability stories for inclusion in EIP knowledge hub (task 2)

Outcomes:

A set of “interoperability stories”, representing practical examples of the impact of EIP flagship services

Interoperability Stories - Overview and Technical Solutions

Over the duration of task 1.1, ELIXIR partners engaged in a programme of outreach and education across ELIXIR nodes and communities, explaining the concept of “interoperability stories” either through presentations at ELIXIR meetings and shared ELIXIR events, or directly through individual engagement. Interested ELIXIR partners were encouraged to bring their interoperability stories to a monthly seminar series that was established as part of the ELIXIR Interoperability Platform meetings.

Over the two years of EIP task 1, nine different interoperability stories were presented, from seven different ELIXIR communities (two presentations were given by the Rare Disease community, and one explored alignment with the EOSC semantic interoperability taskforce). Further interoperability stories have been presented since the end of the reporting period, and these seminars seem to be popular beyond just the Interoperability Platform audience. These interoperability stories are summarised in Table 1, below.

Date	Community Organisation	Title	Speaker
2022-06-14	Intrinsically Disordered Protein	Intrinsically Disordered Protein Community Interoperability Showcase: Exploiting Bioschemas Markup	Alasdair Gray (UK)
2022-07-05	Plant Sciences	Plant Sciences Community Showcase	Cyril Pommier (FR)
2022-09-06	Rare Diseases	Rare Disease Community Interoperability Showcase: examples from EJP RD	Friederike Ehrhart (NL)
2022-10-04	Rare Diseases	Mapping the DCAT-based EJP RD Metadata Model to Bioschemas for improved interoperability	Cesar Bernabe (NL)
2022-12-06	EOSC Semantic Interoperability	User journeys as means of effectively demonstrating value and engaging stakeholders	Wolmar Åkerström (SE)
2023-02-07	Galaxy	Galaxy: a story about interoperability	Bjoern Gruening (DE)
2023-03-07	FAIRtracks	FAIRtracks and Omnipy - FAIRtracks interoperability story	Sveinung Gundersen (NO)
2023-04-04	Single Cell Omics	Single Cell Omics Community Interoperability Showcase	Paulo Czarnewski (SE)
2023-10-03	Metabolomics	Metabolomics Community & Interoperability Platform - On which subjects could they collaborate?	Maria Klapa (GR)

Table 1. The interoperability stories presented by ELIXIR community representatives to the Interoperability Platform Interoperability Stories webinar series.

Presenters were asked to give a presentation that emphasised the key elements of a good interoperability story, which are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The elements of a good interoperability story, emphasising the actions communities took to ensure interoperability, the benefits they hoped those actions would bring, and the wider impact of their work on data sustainability and reuse

Most presentations opened with a use case, highlighting the expected benefits from investment in interoperability work, then described the actions taken and the methods used to improve interoperability within their community. Some also managed to provide evidence of wider impact (i.e. how the community responded through use of new interoperable services or data). Below we give a short summary of each interoperability story presented, emphasising the use case, actions and impact (if available) for each.

Intrinsically Disordered Protein Community Interoperability Showcase: Exploiting Bioschemas Markup

Presenter: Alasdair Gray

Date: 14th June 2022

Community: Intrinsically Disordered Protein

In this presentation, the audience heard how the intrinsically disordered protein community had identified a challenge in discovery and integration of data that spans several experimental fields studying protein structure and function, using methods that are domain specific. As such, there are no comprehensive single resources containing all IDPs. Therefore, researchers wishing to see the combined knowledge from resources such as ModiDB, DisProt and PED encountered an onerous integration task. As a solution, the IDP community proposed the creation of a central knowledge graph that could be asked common queries. To achieve this goal, the IDP described their use of bioschemas, JSON-LD, SPARQL, OpenAIRE and FAIRsharing to assemble a knowledge graph that can be queried by researchers seeking a consolidated, integrated view of data from across the IDP community.

Plant Sciences Community Showcase

Presenter: Cyrill Pommier

Date: 7th May 2022

Community: Plant Sciences

The audience heard Cyril explain how the ELIXIR Plant Community has used standards, including MIAPPE and BrAPI, and tools for interoperability, including COPO, FAIRDOM, pISA-tree, ISA tools, RDMkit and FAIR Cookbook to exchange and integrate plant data and metadata through a BrAPI-powered global portal for federation of heterogenous data. This strategy has been deployed via the FAIDARE system, which facilitates access to genotype and phenotype datasets for crop and forest plants through an easy to use web interface.

Rare Disease Community Interoperability Showcase: examples from EJP RD

Presenter: Friederike Ehrhart

Date: 9th June 2022

Community: Rare Disease

Friederike addressed the fragmentation of knowledge, data and services in the rare disease community, and highlighted the challenge that across this community there are more than 100 valuable resources that need to be brought together to answer research questions. She described several successful technical solutions that have been deployed within the Rare Disease Community (including WikiPathways, BridgeDb and CyTargetLinker) and the importance of being able to connect distinct resources via SPARQL queries and data export. She also highlighted the Community's considerable investment in sourcing good use cases and user requirements in order to align them with technical interoperability solutions via programmes of end user surveys and annual retreats.

Mapping the DCAT-based EJP RD Metadata Model to Bioschemas for improved interoperability

Presenter: Cesar Bernabe

Date: 4th October 2022

Community: Rare Disease

Cesar showcased the use of DCAT (Data Catalog Vocabulary) in the Rare Disease Community through the European Joint Programme on Rare Disease initiative (EJP-RD). The interoperability goal of this programme is to pull together the data from 24 rare disease patient cohorts to support discovery of data; with rare disease, there are very small numbers of patients from whom data is available so a European network of data is highly desirable. Cesar illustrated how DCAT can be used to capture cohort level metadata that facilitates identification of cohorts. He outlined the specific metadata model used to support data collection in EJP-RD community catalogues, and explained their use of other controlled vocabularies for markup, including DCT and FOAF. The EJP-RD community have invested in Bioschemas mappings to support further extraction (from resources implementing the bioschemas model) and dissemination (to portals or aggregators that can consume Bioschemas markup)

User journeys as means of effectively demonstrating value and engaging stakeholders

Presenter: Wolmar Åkerström

Date: 6th December 2022

Community: EOSC Semantic Interoperability Taskforce

In a slightly different type of interoperability story presentation, Wolmar explained the synergy between ELIXIR interoperability stories and the approach the EOSC semantic interoperability task force has taken to capture case studies and use cases. Wolmar described the EOSC library of community use cases, and how this library captures user journeys from different levels. EOSC user journeys are categorised as either real-world case studies; business focused use cases; or task focused use cases. These journeys represent approaches that are individually optimised for their actors, who may be end-users, organisations, data managers or builders. The alignment to ELIXIR interoperability stories was clear and the groups agreed to continue working together into the future to align case studies and interoperability story templates.

Galaxy: a story about interoperability

Presenter: Bjoern Gruening

Date: 7th February 2023

Community: Galaxy

Bjoern highlighted the importance of interoperability to Galaxy users, and the role Galaxy can play in the enhancement of data interoperability from communities. He outlined the role the Galaxy platform plays in enhancing interoperability through embedded support for BioSchemas, Life Science and ORCID based authentication, support for RO-crate and CWL, and more. The audience also heard about support for data ingest and data export features, from public repositories and to workflow platforms like Workflowhub.

FAIRtracks and Omnipy - FAIRtracks interoperability story

Presenter: Sveinung Gundersen

Date: 7th March 2023

Community: FAIRtracks

In this interoperability story seminar, Sveinung gave an overview of how the FAIRtracks initiative aims to improve the FAIRness of genomic track files from a variety of European sources (Ensembl being one of the largest providers). Track files are used to map genomic data to a reference genome and are commonly used in visualisation tools, but are hard to discover (outside of large well known resources) and difficult to compare due to a lack of a central identifier scheme. They often do not contain sufficient content-specific metadata to allow effective reuse of track files from external sources. Sveinung then outlined the interoperability workflow embedded in the FAIRtracks deployment, and how this workflow took advantage of a variety of interoperability resources including Identifiers.org, OLS, RDMkit, and others. He also gave a good summary of how the FAIRtrack deployment has been incorporated into end user tools, including Galaxy and GSuite HyperBrowser. He also highlighted that FAIRtracks itself is an ELIXIR Recommended Interoperability Resource, and explored future work to assign persistent identifiers for tracks that might enhance the impact of this interoperability story

Single Cell Omics Community Interoperability Showcase

Presenter: Paulo Czarnewski

Date: 4th April 2023

Community: Single Cell Omics

In April 2023, the Single Cell Omics Community was relatively newly formed, and Paulo presented a brief overview of the goals of the fledgling community, highlighting that interoperability of single cell data was at the forefront. He provided insight into the main challenges faced by the Community - a diversity of new and exotic methods, for which there are few standards and little convergence in the domain. He also presented complexities in accessing unified data, the fact that processed data was often distributed without original annotation from individual samples, and that open sharing could be a problem due to GDPR restrictions, as much of the data is derived from human subjects. Paulo then presented the work that the Single Cell Omics implementation study (Single Cell Omics Network for ELIXIR, SCONE) was doing to define standards and cross-mappings between standards through workshop programmes, and the goals that could be achieved when data was aligned and distributed within the community in a manner that complied with a lightweight standardised model. He also highlighted that it was early days for the community and that the community hadn't yet been able to validate their results, but future work on interoperability was planned.

Metabolomics Community & Interoperability Platform - On which subjects could they collaborate?

Presenter: Maria Klapa

Date: 3rd October 2023

Community: Metabolomics

In the final interoperability story presented in the reporting period, Maria explained the challenges faced by the Metabolomics Community. She highlighted that the Community, which was formed in 2018, had identified that the major interoperability challenge they face was that of metabolomic model standardisation: this is an issue because much of the work of the metabolomics community requires multi-omic data integration (transcriptomics, proteomics and metabolomics). This integration is difficult without alignment of tools, standards and data resources. She explained the work of the Community implementation study (Fluxomics) and of the MetaboLights resource, especially with regard to the integration of data resources (MetaboLights, UniProt, BioModels, MetabolicAtlas, Rhea, Reactome, BIGG, and <http://pickle.gr/>). Many of the outstanding challenges she describes stem from an absence of standards, and highlighted that future work could focus on development and adoption of standards in metabolomics

Lessons Learned

Positive elements in common across the first round of interoperability stories collected in the reporting period:

1. Start with a use case
2. Find a good data steward who knows the tools
3. Develop data flows, not databases

4. Validate your results
5. Showcase your outcomes so others can follow your lead

Start with a good use case: Good interoperability stories all clearly understand what they're trying to achieve and what the requirements from the data are. Several interoperability stories opened with a clear and succinct summarisation of the goals of the community, and how this mapped into specific use cases that required investment in interoperability, for example, querying across a distributed and poorly harmonised data cohort that was stored in multiple databases

Evidence: IDP, Rare Disease, EOSC community use cases

Find a good data steward who knows the tools: Interoperability stories showed many common elements - including ETL pipelines, construction of knowledge graphs, ontology mapping, workflow descriptions, public data sharing - and these problems have all been solved many times before. Whilst it is not always appropriate or cost-effective to attempt to reuse a previous solution exactly, it is still important to build on the existing state of the art and take advantage of prior knowledge and prior learnings. This is a specialist activity, and the communities that demonstrated positive impact from their interoperability stories acknowledged this and invested in data stewards.

Evidence: Plants, Galaxy, FAIRtracks

Develop data flows, not databases: Many interoperability stories describe processes for transforming, modifying, processing and/or analysing data to make it as usable as possible to the intended audience. The processes described often implicated multiple public repositories and public tools. Good interoperability stories shifted their focus away from data sharing with a single resource and towards a well described, documented and reusable workflow - and in the best cases, this workflow was itself shared via e.g. Workflowhub. Thinking carefully about such workflows, ensuring data is in appropriate public resources at various stages, is a powerful approach. This contrasts with the naive approach many projects take, which is to build a new data silo for their data and then over-optimize (and over-invest in) the data model and the depth of metadata required; whilst efforts to improve and standardise descriptive metadata are admirable, building a new resource offsets these gains by contributing to the data silos problem.

Evidence: Plants, Galaxy, Single Cell Omics, Metabolomics

Validate your results: In the first round of interoperability stories presented, there were several very positive examples of communities checking what they set out to achieve against the results from their interoperability efforts. By actively demonstrating that interoperability work was proving useful, by comparing successful case studies to the original defined use case, several communities were able to ensure they deployed their interoperability resources in the most effective and efficient manner possible.

Evidence: IDP, Galaxy

Showcase your outcomes so others can follow your lead: The interoperability seminar series represents one of the first organised mechanisms to actively share examples of investment in FAIR data management organised around the positive and pragmatic outcomes obtained (rather than the theory of FAIR) within ELIXIR. We have been encouraged to see that others are now seeing the value in this approach, especially through the establishment of the RDM Community. The importance of demonstrating impact is clear, however: most communities should and do reuse strategies and approaches rather than adopting a software or database solution "out of the box" and this requires confidence about the success of a given approach. We therefore encourage the Interoperability Platform and ELIXIR Communities to continue to share their interoperability stories, through forums like the regular interoperability meetings and the annual ELIXIR All Hands Meeting.

Dangers to Avoid

As well as the positive lessons learned, described above, which can be used to guide future interoperability investments made by ELIXIR Communities, the first round of interoperability stories we heard from over the reporting period identified some common pitfalls

- Don't just build it - they won't come
- Don't look to technology for answers

- Don't forget to validate early and often
- Don't build (or reinforce) data silos

Don't just build it - they won't come: All of the stories' authors spoke about the need to develop technology in support of their interoperability challenges. However, many of the presenters and the interoperability platform members discussed that the same problems are solved many times by many different implementations. The seminar series also identified that it is easy to invest heavily in technology in the hope that it will solve problems with interoperability, for example through the creation of expensive, highly curated knowledge graphs with a "one schema to rule them all" approach... but that these efforts are often thwarted by failing to secure buy in from users with simpler problems, and through the difficulty of sustaining complex solutions. A common theme was to identify practical user needs and start small.

Don't look to technology for answers: Similarly to the previous lesson, there are many complex technical implementations available to those interested in interoperability, through ontology mapping tools, triple store technology for databases, knowledge graph building tools, and more. However, the technology rarely becomes the deciding factor as to whether or not an interoperability initiative succeeds. The challenge for most communities lies in managing their data in a way that promotes reuse that goes one step beyond the original intended use of the data. The biggest barrier to this is often found in some basic standards compliant data sharing steps: for example, deposition to an appropriate ELIXIR Core Data Resource or Deposition Database is not always mandated within a community, so rather than aligning data standards to those required by the target resource (therefore ensuring interoperability), groups in communities start the creation of a new technical stack with different data models and data schemas. Heavily investing in new technology most often leads to an entirely new, elegantly modelled data silo, but plagued by the same issues with findability and integration that hampered reuse in the first place.

Don't forget to validate early and often: Once good use cases have been identified, it is important to test interoperability solutions against these use cases as early as possible. For example, satisfying one new user query that wasn't previously possible, even with a minimal implementation, is an extremely valuable demonstrator of success for the chosen approach. The seminar series highlighted the importance of finding these "quick wins" to be sure that approaches are effective; several presenters and discussion topics highlighted wrong steps that could be taken when chasing ever increasing interoperability without checking results against the planned goals. FAIR maturity models, reliable indicators of success, or some other objective metrics can help mitigate this risk.

Don't build (or reinforce) data silos: This is a common problem that many presenters and audience members of the seminar series admitted to having witnessed or even contributed to. A common approach to finding that data in a community is not FAIR enough to support reuse is to attempt to bring all the relevant data "in house", clean it, and then provide a database of the cleaned data. Whilst this can bring short term gains, it usually brings long term problems, as it fragments knowledge, causes data records to fall out of sync or become duplicated, and doesn't promote FAIRness with the groups that generated the data in the first place.

Dissemination and Impact

The nine interoperability stories described as part of the seminar series were presented to an audience of Interoperability Platform members, RDM Community members, and other interested ELIXIR members. Relevant guests have also been directly invited on occasion (e.g. EOSC members). Slides and recordings are freely available to all ELIXIR members via Google Drive, and the outcomes will be further disseminated via Zenodo once author permission is secured. Discussions on lessons learned from interoperability stories have also been held within the EOSC interoperability task force and the Pistoia Alliance FAIR working group.

Originally, we planned to disseminate interoperability stories via the proposed ELIXIR Interoperability KnowledgeHub (task 2), however, plans for the KnowledgeHub deviated somewhat from their initial conception. Task 2 became more focused on expanding the integration between existing interoperability knowledge resources (notably the RDMkit and FAIR cookbook). As such, it became less appropriate and more difficult to organise interoperability

stories into content for the KnowledgeHub. In many cases, there is overlap between the content of interoperability stories and the domain areas in RDMkit (often because the content has been created by the same individuals), and in these cases the interoperability stories may have helped structure some of the observations made in the RDMkit, and vice versa. There is also some conceptual alignment with experience recipes in the FAIR Cookbook. In the next phase of the Programme, we will explore the possibility of better aligning interoperability stories with the relevant public knowledge services in order to find more suitable dissemination forums for lessons learned. The encouragement of best practices across ELIXIR Communities is the aim of Work Package 4 of the 2024-28 Interoperability project plan and could provide a vital avenue for communicating with the wider public.

Adjustments Made

Any extensions, changes in personnel or other alterations from the Project Plan

None necessary.

ELIXIR Interoperability Stories

Collated January 2025

Topic	Title	Speaker
Plant sciences	Plant Sciences Community Showcase	Cyril Pommier (ELIXIR Årance)
Rare diseases	Rare Disease Community Interoperability Showcase: examples from EJP RD	Friederike Ehrhart (ELIXIR Netherlands)
Rare diseases	Mapping the DCAT-based EJP RD Metadata Model to Bioschemas for improved interoperability	Cesar Bernabe (ELIXIR Netherlands)
EOSC semantic interoperability	User journeys as means of effectively demonstrating value and engaging stakeholders	Wolmar Åkerström (ELIXIR Sweden)
Galaxy	Galaxy: a story about interoperability	Bjoern Gruening (ELIXIR Germany)
FAIRtracks	FAIRtracks and Omnipy - FAIRtracks interoperability story	Sveinung Gundersen (ELIXIR Norway)
Metabolomics	Metabolomics Community & Interoperability Platform - On which subjects could they collaborate?	Maria Klapa (ELIXIR Greece)

Plant Sciences Community Showcase

Plant Sciences Community Showcase

Kristina Gruden, Cyril Pommier, Sebastian Beier

July, 2022.

www.elixir-europe.org

Data management and standards outreach

- Successful implementation of plant data and meta data standards
[Minimal Information About Plant Phenotyping Experiment](#)

www.miappe.org

- Many stakeholders & Open Community
 - Elixir, Emphasis, Bioversity, North American PPN
- Breeding API <http://brapi.org/>
- International collaboration :Standard Open Web Service API

Data management and standards outreach

- Successful implementation of plant data and meta data standards
 - Data model
 - Checklist
 - API
 - ontologies
- **Goal:** Widespread adoption of these

Data management and standards outreach & adoption

- Data deposition / publication
 - Web interfaces/tools
 - Guidelines: Plant, 1(2) tools assemblies
 - Training
- Example : FAIRDOM - Seek
 - VIB, ELIXIR-be
 - AGENT project (ELIXIR-fr)

The screenshot shows the AGENT H2020-AGENT project page. At the top, there is a search bar with the text 'Search here...' and a user profile for 'Cyril Pommier'. Below the search bar, there are navigation tabs for 'Dashboard', 'Overview', 'Asset report', and 'Actions'. The main content area contains a paragraph of text: 'All data uploaded to the site is made available to all project partners for the sole purpose of delivering the AGENT project goals. It should not be shared beyond the project without permission of the data generator. Data from this repository may be published via EURISCO and other interfaces under an open source licence at a later date (in accordance with the AGENT Data Management Plan). Documentation:'. Below this text, there are three bullet points: 'Agent data portal (login credentials). Access to list of accessions with Agent_ID', 'AGENT guidelines for dataflow', and 'AGENT Fairdom user manual'. On the right side, there is a section for 'Storage Usage' which states 'The total size of all project assets is: 20.8 GB'.

FAIRDOM Seek organisation

- Investigation organised depending on dataset type
- MIAPPE principles

Selected: [WP3-Phenotypic-Precision-Collection](#) (Investigation)

Description: Please use the [Pheno Experimental Template](<https://urgi.versailles.inrae>)

SEEK ID: <https://urgi.versailles.inrae.fr/investigations/3>

Selected: [WP3-Phenotypic-Historical](#) (Investigation)

Description: Please use the following template: [Eurisco Phenotyping Histor

SEEK ID: <https://urgi.versailles.inrae.fr/investigations/2>

FAIRDOM Seek organisation: Genotype

- Large files (22 GB)
- SCP upload

WP2-Genotypic- Investigation

 Unsubscrib

For VCF files for example.

SEEK ID: <https://urgi.versailles.inrae.fr/investigations/15>

Projects: [H2020-AGENT](#)

Selected: [WP2-Genotypic-Investigation](#) (Investigation)

Description: For VCF files for example.

SEEK ID: <https://urgi.versailles.inrae.fr/investigations/15>

Tools for data and metadata exchange

- History of working with ISA Tab
- Need of a RO Crate for plant
 - MIAPPE (biologists oriented)
 - ISA (general omics ?)

- Knowledge Graphs
 - Bioschemas & MIAPPE

Global Data Portal for heterogenous data federation

Dedicated plant data search engine

FAIDARE

21 heterogenous data sources

Pre production: <https://staging-urgi.versailles.inrae.fr/faidare/>

The screenshot shows the FAIDARE web interface. At the top, there is a header with the FAIDARE logo and the text "URGI More...". Below the header, the main content area is titled "FAIR Data-finder for Agronomic REsearch". On the left side, there are three filter sections:

- Taxon group (1,886)**: A search box labeled "Filter on Taxon group...".
- Data type (39)**: A search box labeled "Filter on Data type...".
- Database (32)**: A search box labeled "Filter on Database...".

On the right side, there is a search bar with the text "Examples: yield, fhb" and a "Search" button. Below the search bar, there is a section for "Example queries".

FAIDARE

- Extract Transform Load Workflow
 - Centralized index
- Metadata harmonisation
- Many scripts and tools maintained by ELIXIR-fr
- Moving to Lark templating language to full python

<https://github.com/elixir-europe/plant-brapi-etl-faidare>

Plant interoperability needs

- Deposition, validation, interfaces, etc...
 - Fairdom Seek
 - Dataverse/eDale/Zenodo
 - Validation using frictionless (AGENT, WUR)
 - EBI databases
- Data exchange
 - Databases to tools and back
 - RO Crate
- Collaboration in place
 - ELIXIR IS
 - ELIXIR Converge
 - Agroserv
 - Biohackathon
 - Others ?

Aknowledgments

H2020 AGENT

N. Stein (IPK, coord), P. Kersey (RBGK), M. Alaux (INRAE), S. Weise (IPK), C. Pommier (INRAE), M. Lange (IPK), R. Finkers (WUR), J. Dooly (INRAE)

elixir

Elixir Plant community & platforms

Beier S., Gruden C., Pommier C., Coppens F., Schol. U., Lange M., Contreras B., Adam Blondon AF, Faria D, Chavez I, Miguel C, Droedsbek B, Finkers R, Papoutsoglou E, Olster R, Ramsak Z, ...

MIAPPE community

ELIXIR Plant Community,
Krajewsky P, Cwiek H, Tardieu F, Usadel B, Arend D, Arnaud E, Junker A, King G, Laporte MA, Poorter H, Reif J, Rocca-Serra P, Sansone SA, Kersey P,
And many more!

Breeding API

Selby P, Mueller L, Robbins K, Backlund JE, ... ,
And many more!

Crop Ontology

Arnaud E, Laporte MA, ...

Emphasis

Tardieu F, Usadel B, Arend D, Junker A, Poorter H, Neveu P, Pierushka R, Shur U...
And many more!

Rare Disease Community Interoperability Showcase: examples from EJP RD

Rare Disease Community Interoperability Showcase: examples from EJP RD

06.09.2022 Friederike Ehrhart
ELIXIR-NL, Maastricht University

European Life Sciences Infrastructure for Biological Information
www.elixir-europe.org

Challenges in rare disease data analysis

- **Fragmentation:**
~100 resources (infrastructures, catalogs, tools) analyzed
~ Knowledge
- **Lack of adaptation** to RD research needs:
~70% are not RD specific, but of interest to RD
- **Lack of interoperability** between resources
- **Scarce collaboration** between resources
- **Lack of structured data** for use in analysis tools
- **Lacking awareness** of RD community about resources
Surveys: 50-90% of resources like ELIXIR CDR unknown to RD researchers

Successful applications for interoperability

- WikiPathways – biomedical literature/knowledge -> machine readable pathways
 - Rare Disease portal (110 pathways), Lipids portal (collaboration with LipidMaps - ELIXIR Implementation study on curation)
- BridgeDb – identifier mapping between databases
 - Genes and gene products, chemical compounds, under construction: microRNA and diseases
- CyTargetLinker – extension of networks with database information
 - PPI, drug – target, microRNA – target, gene – transcription factor, gene – disease
- EJP RD virtual platform (under construction)
 - Patient registries, clinical study information
 - Knowledge base – linking to different databases (Orphanet, CelloSaurus, WikiPathways)

WikiPathways

WIKIPATHWAYS
Pathways for the People

Downloadable
content
SPARQL endpoint
API

Export to Cytoscape via app
-> network creation from
pathways

4

search

- Help
- About us
- Contact us
- Report a bug
- How to cite
- Quality control
- Development
- WikiPathways Blog
- Curation Events

download

- Download files
- Other file formats
- Web service API
- WikiPathways RDF
- Embed code

activity

- Browse pathways
- Recent changes
- New releases
- New pathways
- Edit pathways
- Create pathway
- Statistics

tools

Wikipathways.org

Log in / create account

page discussion view source history

Share your pathway knowledge in the fight against COVID-19

ACCESS the rapidly growing collection of COVID-19 pathways, CONTRIBUTE your time and domain knowledge about pathway biology as a pathway author, and USE these pathways in your research.

Welcome to WikiPathways

WikiPathways is a database of biological pathways maintained by and for the scientific community.

Read about our 12-year journey so far and official exit from beta or our 2021 NAR paper

Find Pathways

Search

Search

You can search by:

- Pathway name (*Apoptosis*)
- Gene or protein name (*p53*)
- Any page content (*cancer*)

Browse

Get Pathways

Download

Download by sp
Access by API

Today's Featured Pathway

Host-pathogen interaction of human coronaviruses - autophagy (Homo sapiens)

Published online 19 November 2020

Nucleic Acids Research, 2021, Vol. 49, Database issue D613–D621
doi: 10.1093/nar/gkaa1024

WikiPathways: connecting communities

Marvin Martens¹, Ammar Ammar¹, Anders Riutta², Andra Waagmeester³,
Denise N. Slenter¹, Kristina Hanspers², Ryan A. Miller¹, Daniela Digles⁴,
Elisson N. Lopes⁵, Friederike Ehrhart¹, Lauren J. Dupuis¹, Laurent A. Winckers¹,
Susan L. Coort¹, Egon L. Willighagen¹, Chris. T. Evelo^{1,6}, Alexander R. Pico² and
Martina Kutmon^{1,6,*}

7q11.23 copy number variation syndrome (Homo sapiens)

Friederike Ehrhart, Egon Willighagen

FKBP6

Annotated with: [ENSG00000077800](#)
(Ensembl)

Find pathways with FKBP6...

External references:

- Affy
 - 3057159
 - TC07003330.hg
 - 8133293
 - 38137 at
- Agilent
- Ensembl
- Entrez Gene
- GeneOntology
- HGNC
- Illumina
- OMIM
- PDB
- RefSeq
- UCSC Genome Browser
- Uniprot-TrEMBL
- WikiGenes

Literature references

Annotated, machine readable interactions

Pathway, disease and cell type ontology

Integration of knowledge leads to unexpected findings

Prader-Willi syndrome and Angelman syndrome: Visualisation of the molecular pathways for two chromosomal disorders

Friederike Ehrhart ^b

SCIENTIFIC DATA

OPEN DATA DESCRIPTOR **A catalogue of 863 Rett-syndrome-causing *MECP2* mutations and lessons learned from data integration**

SCIENTIFIC DATA

OPEN DATA DESCRIPTOR **A resource to explore the discovery of rare diseases and their causative genes**

Friederike Ehrhart^{1,2,3}, Egon L. Willighagen¹, Martina Kutmon^{1,3}, Max van Hoften¹, Leopold M. G. Curfs² & Chris T. Evelo^{1,2,3}

Original Investigation

Integrated analysis of human transcriptome data for Rett syndrome finds a network of involved genes

Friederike Ehrhart ², Lars Eijssen, Elisa Cirillo, Eric E. Smeets, Nasim Bahram Sangani,

Received 03 Oct 2018, Accepted 06 Mar 2019, Accepted author version posted online: 25 Mar 2019

Converging pathways found in copy number variation syndromes with high schizophrenia risk

¹ David E.J. Linden

doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2022.02.07.479370>

This article is a preprint and has not been certified by peer review [what does this mean?].

REVIEW

Open Access

Rett syndrome – biological pathways leading from *MECP2* to disorder phenotypes

Friederike Ehrhart^{1,2*} ¹, Susan L. M. Coort², Elisa Cirillo², Eric Smeets¹, Chris T. Evelo^{1,2} and Leopold M. G. Curfs¹

Standardised access to Identifier Mappings

BridgeDb is a framework to map identifiers between various biological databases and related resources. These mappings are provided for genes, proteins, metabolites, metabolic reactions, diseases, complexes and publications. BridgeDb includes a Java library that provides an API for programmatic access.

NEWS: Find the latest tutorials on BridgeDb in the FAIR-plus cookbook [here](#).

Contributing organisations

Current coverage:

- Genes, gene products
- Chemical compounds
- Interactions

Under discussion/construction

- Diseases
- microRNA
- ***Upgrade for SNPs (gene variants in general)***

<https://bridgedb.github.io/>

BridgeDb plug-ins

- **Cytoscape:** <http://apps.cytoscape.org/apps/bridgedb>
- **PathVisio:** <http://www.pathvisio.org/plugin/bridgedbconfig-plugin/>
- **R:**
<http://bioconductor.org/packages/devel/bioc/html/BridgeDbR.html> (source:
<https://github.com/BiGCAT-UM/bridgedb-r>)

RECENT POSTS

CyTargetLinker automation feature release

A microRNA Signature Associated with Early Recurrence in Breast Cancer.

CyTargetLinker publication in PLoS One

WELCOME

Extend your biological networks in Cytoscape with our CyTargetLinker app

Tutorials

[How to use CyTargetLinker.](#)

Learn how to use CyTargetLinker by going through one of our tutorials.

Currently available:

Drugs (DrugBank)

Transcription factors (ENCODE)

miRNA (MirTarBase)

Chemical compounds (ChEMBL)

Pathways

(WikiPathways/Reactome)

Rare diseases (OMIM, Orphanet)

SOFTWARE TOOL ARTICLE

REVISED CyTargetLinker app update: A flexible solution for network extension in Cytoscape [version 2; peer review: 2 approved]

Martina Kutmon ^{1,2}, Friederike Ehrhart ^{1,3}, Egon L. Willighagen ¹,
Chris T. Evelo ^{1,2}, Susan L. Coort ¹

SCIENTIFIC DATA

Check for updates

OPEN

DATA DESCRIPTOR

A resource to explore the discovery of rare diseases and their causative genes

Friederike Ehrhart ^{1,2,3}, Egon L. Willighagen ¹, Martina Kutmon ^{1,3}, Max van Hoften ¹, Leopold M. G. Curfs ² & Chris T. Evelo ^{1,2,3}

Disease networks

Possibility to create complex networks and analyse them is a result of good data and knowledge resource interoperability

- Knowledge driven (e.g. from pathways or PPIs)
- Data driven (e.g. Co-expression analysis)
- Combinations thereof

Cytoscape
(WikiPathways app)

EJP RD Virtual platform

- A **service-oriented middleware** providing an **eco-system of inter-linked web services** to foster and facilitate RD research
- **Distributed and federated by design**, with services provided from servers all across Europe
- makes extensive use of **pre-existing standards**
- follows **FAIR principles** (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)
- adheres to established **quality and sustainability criteria**
- **Services** include but are not limited to:
 - ✓ Authentication and Authorization
 - ✓ Services for data discovery, querying and data catalogues
 - ✓ Services for data linkage, patient registration and consent management
 - ✓ Services for data analysis

Assess and address the needs of the community

End-user surveys in 2019 & 2020; 742 respondents

Objectives

WIKIPATHWAYS
Pathways for the People

Create resources for RD molecular pathways

Genetic variants and their embedding into systems biology analysis

Influence of environmental factors (nutrition, toxicology and drugs) to RD patients that takes their special, modified metabolism and signalling pathways into account

Building RD networks for better understanding of the disease and potential drug repurposing

Final Products

Rare disease pathways and portal on WikiPathways database [\[LINK\]](#)

Workflows to analyse multi-omics rare disease data

- Including genetic variant data
- Including toxicology, nutritional and drug data

Rare disease networks publicly available on Ndex database [\[LINK\]](#)

Thank you for your attention

Prof. Chris T. Evelo
Theodoros Zarotiadis
Dr. Lars Eijssen
Dr. Martina Kutmon
Aishwarya Iyer

Dr. Susan Coort
Dr. Egon Willighagen
Marvin Martens
Denise Slenter
Woosub Shin

INSERM: Dr. Ana Rath, Dr. Marc Hanauer
University Aix-Marseille: Dr. Ozan Ozisik, Morgane Trezol, Prof. Anas Baudot
University Hospital Heidelberg: Prof. Franz Schfer
Radboud University Nijmegen: Prof. Peter-Bram t'Hon
Leiden University Medical Centre: Dr. Eleni Mina, Dr. Marco Roos

**Mapping the DCAT-based EJP RD Metadata
Model to Bioschemas for improved
interoperability**

Mapping the DCAT-based EJP RD Metadata Model to Bioschemas for improved interoperability

César Bernabé, Rajaram Kaliyaperumal and Marco Roos

Hi, Elixir!

About me:

Foundational Ontologies to improve interoperability between systems goals and requirements specification languages

PhD at the Biosemantics Group:

- "**Goal-models to support FAIR implementation** decisions and (meta)data conceptual modelling"
- **Foundational Ontologies** to increase the FAIRness of data and models.

EJP RD FAIRification Steward

The EJP RD and FAIRification Stewards

Liaising registries around Europe for better rare diseases research

- 24 ERN registries specialised in different groups of rare diseases
- Technical support, knowledge/experience exchange, training, advising on standards for the RD
- Supporting registries being interoperable with the life sciences research community

license [CC0-1.0](#) tag [v1.2.0](#) funder [EJP RD](#)

Metadata for EJP rare disease patient registries, biobanks and catalogs

As part of the [European Joint Programme \(EJP\) for Rare Disease](#), we are developing standards for rare disease registries to describe their metadata that will improve the FAIR-ness of these resources.

The EJP RD Metadata Model

- **Organisation** - describes a organisation
- **Location** - describes a location
- **Catalog** - describes a resource catalog
- **Resource** - describes any digital resource
 - **Patient Registry** - describes a patient registry
 - **Biobank** - describes a biobank
 - **Guideline** - describes a guideline
 - **Dataset** - describes a dataset

class Resource Metadata Schema

The EJP RD Metadata Model (Simplified View)

EJP RD - Bioschemas Mapping (v1.0)

Properties were also mapped, not shown on these slides for the sake of simplicity.

Demo

EJP RD - Bioschemas Mapping (v1.0)

EJP RD - Bioschemas Mapping (v1.0)

EJP RD - Bioschemas Mapping (v1.1) - Including SKOS

Broader Mapping

Closer Mapping

broadMatch

narrowMatch

closeMatch

exactMatch

EJP RD - Bioschemas Mapping (v1.1) - Including SKOS

- Still, there is loss of semantics
- SKOS x OWL
- Queries are not "natural"

EJP RD - Bioschemas Mapping (v1.1) - Including SKOS

- Still, there is loss of semantics
- SKOS x OWL
- Queries are not "natural"

EJP RD Metadata Model and Mapping

Online Documentation

<https://bit.ly/3SMXkoR>

license [CC0-1.0](#) tag [v1.2.0](#) funder [EJP RD](#)

Metadata for EJP rare disease patient registries, biobanks and catalogs

As part of the [European Joint Programme \(EJP\) for Rare Disease](#), we are developing standards for rare disease registries to describe their metadata that will improve the FAIR-ness of these resources.

license [CC0-1.0](#) funder [EJP RD](#)

ejprd-metadata-bioschema-mappings

This repository contains the mappings between the [EJPRD metadata model](#) and the bioschemas.org model.

The mapping

The mapping file contains both OWL-based mappings and SKOS-based mappings. The latter is used to provide a more accurate semantic to the mappings, as some OWL-based mappings (e.g., owl:sameAs) might be too strict. Still, we maintained the OWL-based mappings to provide an automatic machine-actionable translation of the EJP RD metadata resources to bioschema.org concepts.

<https://bit.ly/3C6Qlds>

Contributors

Rajaram Kaliyaperumal

Marco Roos

Question

A Schema.org Type

Thing > CreativeWork > Comment > Question

A specific question - e.g. from a user seeking answers online, or collected in a Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ) document.

User journeys as means of effectively demonstrating value and engaging stakeholders

Case studies and use cases

User journeys as means of effectively demonstrating value and engaging stakeholders

Engagement of research communities and service providers in EOSC

EOSC Symposium, Prague, Czech Republic

15 November 2022

Presented by Peter Maccallum (ELIXIR)
on behalf of Wolmar Nyberg Åkers tröm (ELIXIR Sweden)
and the EOSC Semantic Interoperability TF

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons
Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivatives 4.0 International

<https://doi.org/10.17044/scilifelab.21542313>

Journeys come in many shapes

Use cases and case studies can demonstrate value and engage stakeholders in requirements gathering

Use cases and communities

ELIXIR draws on communities to share success stories and define use cases for its services

Semantic interoperability use cases

Provide 1) input to the initiatives that are shaping EOSC and 2) examples and lessons learned to stakeholders

Use cases demonstrate value

Prevalent in contexts ranging from product sales, to EOSC projects, and healthcare governance

Adopters recognise themselves

Used in requirements gathering and communication

Builders can see the full picture

Used in development and validation of services

Policy can ensure representation

Mapping the landscape of stakeholders and how they are served by different use cases

Community Use Cases | EOSC

https://eosc-portal.eu/eosc-in-practice/use-cases

Home » Use Cases » Community Use Cases

Community Use Cases

This page provides examples of "EOSC in practice" use cases or success stories that highlight how EOSC services and resources can support the daily work of researchers and innovators. Please scroll down to make the use cases appear.

If you wish to share your EOSC use case, please [fill out the webform](#).

Run4science.org - Measuring environmental and biodiversity data... while running!

We want citizens to measure their environment by using smartphones. Most of the citizen science initiatives are focused on one topic: it can be air quality, biodiversity.

Kampal Artificial Intelligence for rare disease diagnosis

In the context of the EOSC-hub project, Kampal Data Solutions is benefitting from storing the healthy and ill patients' registries to a database on EOSC infrastructure.

Guardomic- bot mitigation engine

Web services owners struggle daily to protect their websites from bot traffic and their users from fraudulent digital ads or cryptocurrency web mining.

BBC | Research & Development

ELIXIR and the life sciences community

https://eosc-portal.eu/elixir-and-life-scienc

ELIXIR and the life sciences community

[Go to Website](#)

Engineering & Technology

Natural Sciences

Societal challenges

ELIXIR is an organisation aiming to coordinate, integrate and sustain bioinformatics resources – such as databases, computational services, applications – across its member states and enables users in academia and industry to access what is vital for their research.

The challenge is to unite Europe's leading life science organisations in managing the increasing volume of data generated by publicly-funded research.

Technical challenges

ELIXIR wants to establish a federation of cloud sites, each providing storage and compute capacity for researchers. An established Competence Centre in EOSC-hub is supporting this activity. The CC team has been supporting ELIXIR to set up a compute platform that allows ELIXIR cloud and data providers to share cloud compute and storage capacity to replicate and share reference datasets with each other and with their users.

How EOSC can help and add value

The ELIXIR Compute Platform aims to enable researchers to combine technical components of the platform services into a seamless ecosystem, creating a science-ready interface to the key resources and technological capabilities that are available for life sciences.

The ELIXIR Compute Platform has been leveraging the EOSC Service Catalogue, especially in the area of aligning ELIXIR with the EOSC AAI.

Share this:

Case studies are real-world scenarios

Actual people and organisations adopting a solution in a specific context and outcomes of their efforts

Use cases can be business focused

How a stakeholder group can approach adopting a solution to achieve broader goals and outcomes

Use cases can be task focused

How a user interacts with different services and resources to complete a task

Conceptual models tie them together

Actors, components and resources involved and how they relate to more general categories

Capturing case studies and use cases

Encourage the wider EOSC stakeholder community to contribute interesting and representative examples

Indexing for adopters and builders

Compare and consolidate across stakeholders, tasks, goals and component of the EOSC IF

Representing the EOSC community

Identify and fill gaps in the types of organisations, domains and goals captured by the task force

Task Force Charter

Semantic Interoperability

Introduction

EOSC and semantic interoperability
Challenges to semantic interoperability

Main aims

Objectives

- O1: Explorations into Semantic Interoperability
- O2: Knowledge exchange around Semantic Interoperability
- O3: Recommendations

Core activities of the Task Force

Planned duration of the Task Force

Working methodology

Explorations/Case Studies

Methods

Output

Dependencies

Membership

References

APPENDIX

Case studies (examples)

Guide initiatives through journeys

Coordination and steering through the TFs could be better with a shared vision and comprehensive picture

Host a shared task force catalogue

Keeping accumulated case studies in one place could increase their visibility and avoid redundant efforts

Promote best practices and resources

Pooling experiences, procedures and skills will help TF members focus on content over process

Liaise between EOSC projects and TFs

Creating opportunities to communicate can foster further collaboration and synergies

**EOSC Association
AISBL**

Rue du Luxembourg 3
BE-1000 Brussels, Belgium
+32 2 537 73 18
info@eosc.eu | www.eosc.eu
Reg. number: 0755 723 931
VAT number: BE0755 723 931

Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström

EOSC Semantic Interoperability TF

Data steward, ELIXIR Sweden / NBIS, SciLifeLab

wolmar.n.akerstrom@uu.se

Peter Maccallum

Chief Technical Officer, ELIXIR

peter.maccallum@elixir-europe.org

Galaxy: a story about interoperability

Galaxy: a story about interoperability

much more than a workflow management system

www.elixir-europe.org

Abstraction layers

Data Types and metadata

data provenance storage

Storage (Posix, ObjectStore ...)

User Interfaces
(different user groups)

Tools

Reference data

Compute
(HPC, Cloud-Computing,
GPGPU ...)

Data exports
(bag-it, RO-crate ...)

Metrics

Visualisations

Data imports

Tool installation
(modules, Docker, Singularity,
Conda, ...)

Authentication & Authorization

General framework interop

- OpenAPI
- AAI, OIDC, ORCID
- make storage interoperable by supporting and transparently offering plenty of different storage engines (S3, iRODS, Posix)
- export of citations of all used in bibtex
- Bioschemas in (GTN, Galaxy tools ...)
- Reference data
- Authentication & Authorization

- 3100+ tools
- Every day a new one
- Tools have a short lifetime
- Not very well maintained
- Not very well optimized

Tools and the tool form

- tools on its own is a means to unify the UI of every tool → UX
- tools are usually constructed in a way that make them interoperable with other tools
- inputs and outputs are annotated by filetype → EDAM
- DOIs for tools
- xref for various other resources, like Bioconductor, bio.tools
- requirements are defined generalistic → Galaxy finds conda, containers depending on the infra

Citations: 📄

- Love, M. I., Huber, W., & Anders, S. (2014). Moderated estimation of fold change and dispersion for RNA-seq data with DESeq2. *Genome Biology*, 15(12). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13059-014-0550-8> 📄

Requirements: ?

- bioconductor-deseq2 (Version 1.34.0)
- bioconductor-rhdf5 (Version 2.38.0)
- bioconductor-tximport (Version 1.22.0)
- bioconductor-genomicfeatures (Version 1.46.1)
- r-getopt (Version 1.20.3)
- r-ggrepel (Version 0.9.1)
- r-gplots (Version 3.1.1)
- r-pheatmap (Version 1.0.12)
- r-rjson (Version 0.2.20)

References:

- bio.tools: DESeq2 (bio.tools 📄) (OpenEBench 📄)

The screenshot shows a 'Tools' section of a web application. At the top right, there is a star icon and a dropdown arrow. Below this is a search bar with the text 'search tool'. A dropdown menu is open, showing a refresh icon and the text 'Full Tool Panel'. Below that, it says '...by Ontology' followed by a checkmark icon and 'EDAM Operations', and a network icon and 'EDAM Topics'. The main content area below the menu is divided into sections: 'ALIGNMENT' (partially visible), 'Sequence', 'ANALYSIS', 'Sequence conversion', 'Sequence masking', and 'Sequence assembly validation'. The 'ANALYSIS' section is highlighted with a grey background.

So people can...

featureCounts Measure gene expression in RNA-Seq experiments from SAM or BAM files (Galaxy Version 2.0.1+galaxy2)

Please provide a value for this option.

Alignment file

No bam or sam dataset available.

The input alignment file(s) where the gene expression has to be counted. The file can have a SAM or BAM format; but ALL files must be in the same format. Unless you are using a Gene annotation file from the History, these files must have the database/genome attribute already specified e.g. hg38, not the default: ?

Specify strand information

Unstranded

Indicate if the data is stranded and if strand-specific read counting should be performed. Strand setting must be the same as the strand settings used to produce the mapped BAM input(s) (-s)

Gene annotation file

locally cached

Using locally cached annotation

No options available

If the annotation file you require is not listed here, please contact the Galaxy administrator

Output format

Gene-ID "1" read-count (MultiQC/DESeq2/edgeR/lmma-voom compatible)

The output format will be tabular, select the preferred columns here

Create gene-length file

No

Creates a tabular file that contains the effective (nucleotides used for counting reads) length of the feature; might be useful for estimating FPKM/RPKM

Options for paired-end reads

Read filtering options

Advanced options

Email notification

No

Send an email notification when the job completes.

featureCounts

...instead of

live.usegalaxy.eu :: right here, right now!

The Interop of data

Datasets:

- every dataset has metadata associated
- datasets are stored in an object store abstraction layer to support
- datatypes (EDAM, type and annotation), but also column, hdf5 layers, sqlite tables etc ...
- conversion tools to convert one type to another

Data export and import:

- RO-Crate export
- BCO export

The screenshot shows the Galaxy web interface. The top navigation bar includes 'Galaxy', 'Workflow', 'Visualize', 'Shared Data', 'Help', 'User', and a 'Using 33%' indicator. The main content area is titled 'Workflow Invocations' and displays a table of workflow runs.

Workflow	History	Invoked	Updated	State
Test workflow	Large history	5 days ago	5 days ago	scheduled
Test workflow	History with workflow	about 2 months ago	about 2 months ago	scheduled

data in

- Posix ((s)ftp(s), data-library, unix-users)
- webdav
- dropbox
- → plugin infrastructure!

- Tools can import data
- Omero integration
- OmicsDI, Seek
- Intermine

GA4GH and APIs

Read more in <https://galaxyproject.org/ga4gh/>

Currently supported GA4GH standards:

- DRS
- TRS
- TES
- Beacon (<https://galaxyproject.org/news/2023-01-beacon-integration/>)

OpenAPI support all way down.
More than 500 API endpoints.

workflows

- export in RO-Crate + CWL-abstract
- work on CWL support continues
- DOI for workflows via WorkflowHub → TRS
- SPDX IDs for licenses for workflows

workflows (the async ones)

class: GalaxyWorkflow

doc: |

Simple workflow that no-op cats a file

inputs:

the_input:

type: File

doc: input doc

outputs:

the_output:

outputSource: cat/out_file1

steps:

cat:

tool_id: cat1

doc: cat doc

in:

input1: the_input

workflows - running

Command-line utilities to assist in developing [Galaxy](#) and [Common Workflow Language](#) tools.

Workflow: XChem combined

Run workflow

History Options

Send results to a new history

Yes No

1: Receptor

49: Mpro-x1093_0_apo-desolv.pdb

2: Active site

48: Mpro-x1093.as

3: Candidate ligands

46: EnumeratedCandidates (v4)

4: Reference molecules

47: hits.sdf

5: XChem Docking

6: XChem TransFS Scoring

7: XChem SuCOS Scoring

> pl anemo r un gal axy. ym

workflows - reports in markdown

The screenshot displays the Galaxy / MK web interface. The top navigation bar includes 'Galaxy / MK', 'Analyze Data', 'Workflow', 'Visualize', 'Shared Data', 'Admin', 'Help', 'User', and 'Using 801.6 MB'. The left sidebar lists various tool categories: Tools, Circos, Get Data, Collection Operations, XYZ, asdfasdfsdf, require_txt, Text Manipulation, Convert Formats, Filter and Sort, Join, Subtract and Group, Fetch Alignments/Sequences, Operate on Genomic Intervals, and Statistics. The main content area is titled 'Workflow: Unnamed workflow' and features a 'Run workflow' button. Below this, the 'History Options' section includes a toggle for 'Send results to a new history' with 'Yes' and 'No' buttons. The workflow steps are listed in a table:

Step	Tool/Command	View	Edit	Delete
1	somedata	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6	gffread on data 5: gff3	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	outputdata (Galaxy Version 0.0.1)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

The right sidebar shows the 'History' section with a search bar and a list of datasets. The 'Unnamed history' section displays '4 shown, 9 deleted' and '5.3 MB'. The dataset list includes:

- 6: gffread on data 5: gff3
- 5: ecoli-k12.gff3
- 4: gffread on data 1: gff3
- 1: Galaxy2-[E_coli_str_K-12_substr_MG1655_genes].gff3

Abstraction layers

Data Types and metadata

data provenance storage

Storage (Posix, ObjectStore ...)

User Interfaces
(different user groups)

Tools

Reference data

Compute
(HPC, Cloud-Computing,
GPGPU ...)

Data exports
(bag-it, RO-crate ...)

Metrics

Visualisations

Data imports

Authentication & Authorization

Tool installation
(modules, Docker, Singularity,
Conda, ...)

thanks

FAIRtracks and Omnipy - FAIRtracks interoperability story

FAIRtracks and Omnipy

- *FAIRtracks interoperability story*

March 7, 2023
Sveinung Gundersen

www.elixir-europe.org

Genomic tracks

Any genomic data file mapped to a reference genome coordinate system!
- Not only for visual analysis!

- Gene regions, repeating elements, conserved regions
- Chromatin accessibility (e.g., DNase I Hypersensitivity)
- Binding of Transcription Factors to DNA
- Histone modifications along DNA
- Gene expression, Gene fusion, Transcription start sites (TSS)
- Cis-regulatory elements (promoters, enhancers...)
- DNA methylation
- 3D genome structure
- GWAS SNPs for disease, SNVs and CNVs in cancer

Important goals for FAIRtracks

Findable

- Global identifiers for track files, as well as track collections, studies, samples, and experiments
- Search and import of individual track files across repositories, also repositories not supported by consortia data portals
- Search using formal (non-free-text) queries

Accessible

- Easy (automated) retrieval of track data
- Persistence of track data and versioned metadata

Interoperable

- Lack of standard metadata model with practically useful attributes
- Annotation using community-accepted vocabularies/ontologies
- Cross-references to records in relevant (meta)data repositories

Reusable

- Support for detailed context-specific metadata content together with standardised summary attributes
- Simple process for data providers to submit data and metadata that at the same time accommodates the required stringency for (automated) downstream usability
- Easily available data usage licenses
- Detailed provenance of experimental and *in silico* analysis steps

FAIRtracks (tool assembly)

- Represents a secondary iteration of the data life cycle (as defined in RDMkit)
- FAIRtracks (more-or-less) begins when the primary data life cycle ends

Tool integration

- TrackFind client implemented in GSuite HyperBrowser:
 - https://hyperbrowser.uio.no/trackfind_test (search for tool "trackfind")
- JSON and GSuite (<http://gtrack.no>) formats as metadata / search result exchange format
- Search results can be transferred to the HyperBrowser server, preprocessed, and used in statistical analyses
- Integration into vanilla Galaxy under development

TrackFind client

Select repository: Blueprint - Blueprint

Select attribute: samples

 |_ sample_type

 |_ term_value

Selection type: Single selection

Select value: naive B cell

Select attribute: experiments

 |_ tech_type

 |_ term_value

Selection type: Single selection

Select value: CHIP-seq assay

Select attribute: --- Select ---

Select type of data

[Check all](#) [Uncheck all](#)

Annotation track [107 files found]

Select tracks: Keep all tracks

Track title	Type of data	Cell/tissue type	Target	Genome build	File format
H3K27me3 on naive B cell (16)	Annotation track	naive B cell	H3K27_trimethylation_site	GRCh38	bigWig
H3K36me3 on naive B cell (6)	Annotation track	naive B cell	H3K36_trimethylation_site	GRCh38	bigWig
H3K4me1 on naive B cell (7)	Annotation track	naive B cell	H3K4_monomethylation_site	GRCh38	bigBed
H3K4me1 on naive B cell (13)	Annotation track	naive B cell	H3K4_monomethylation_site	GRCh38	bigBed
H3K4me3 on naive B cell (8)	Annotation track	naive B cell	H3K4_trimethylation	GRCh38	bigBed
H3K36me3 on naive B cell (10)	Annotation track	naive B cell	H3K36_trimethylation_site	GRCh38	bigWig

Expand table (now showing 6 of 107 rows)...

Include non-standard attributes in search results: No

Execute

Tool integration

- Analysis example
 - Sites of open chromatin for various cell types from BLUEPRINT (DNaseI HS)
 - Set of variants associated with Multiple Sclerosis (MS)
 - Which cell types are most relevant to MS? (i.e., where do the variants overlap the most with open chromatin?)

CALCULATE P-VALUES PER TRACK IN SUITE: IS A TRACK IN THE SUITE MORE SIMILAR TO THE QUERY TRACK THAN EXPECTED BY CHANCE? (MC)

The track "Chromatin Accessibility on CD8-positive, alpha-beta T cell" has the lowest P-value of 0.0196 corresponding to 2.3027 similarity to the query track "sample track with Multiple Sclerosis-associated regions, expanded 10kb in both directions" as measured by "Forbes coefficient: ratio of observed to expected overlap" track similarity measure.

Import table to history (tabular) Import GSuite with results to history

Show instructions for table

Rank	samples->sample_type->term_value	Track title	Similarity to query track	P-value	Overlap between query and reference track (bps)	Genome coverage of track (bps)	Nr. of reference track elements	experiments->global_id	studies->global_id	samples->global_id
1	CD8-positive, alpha-beta T cell	Chromatin Accessibility on CD8-positive, alpha-beta T cell	2.30265525086	0.0196078431373	24068	28313904	104191	EGA.EXPERIMENT:EGAX00001291466	EGA.STUDY:EGAS00001000351	BIOSAMPLE:SAMEA2049928
2	CD4-positive, alpha-beta T cell	Chromatin Accessibility on CD4-positive, alpha-beta T cell	2.13405247706	0.0196078431373	31279	39704199	140093	EGA.EXPERIMENT:EGAX00001293540	EGA.STUDY:EGAS00001000351	BIOSAMPLE:SAMEA2168549
3	lymphocyte of B lineage	Chromatin Accessibility on Acute Lymphocytic Leukemia - CTR	1.9458482673	0.0196078431373	72902	101489040	365372	EGA.EXPERIMENT:EGAX00001336932	EGA.STUDY:EGAS00001000351	BIOSAMPLE:SAMEA3515731
4	myeloid cell	Chromatin Accessibility on Acute Myeloid Leukemia	1.81886689204	0.0196078431373	29343	43701090	163134	EGA.EXPERIMENT:EGAX00001336930	EGA.STUDY:EGAS00001000351	BIOSAMPLE:SAMEA3556817
5	macrophage	Chromatin Accessibility on macrophage - T=6days LPS	1.68996259661	0.078431372549	24449	39189767	144520	EGA.EXPERIMENT:EGAX00001215903	EGA.STUDY:EGAS00001000954	BIOSAMPLE:SAMEA2733979
6	CD14-positive, CD16-negative classical monocyte	Chromatin Accessibility on CD14-positive, CD16-negative classical monocyte	1.55794706897	0.078431372549	48116	83661470	291808	EGA.EXPERIMENT:EGAX00001403040	EGA.STUDY:EGAS00001000351	BIOSAMPLE:SAMEA3215810
7	macrophage	Chromatin Accessibility on macrophage - T=6days B-	1.58039523016	0.117647058824	58308	99942707	343319	EGA.EXPERIMENT:EGAX00001215904	EGA.STUDY:EGAS00001000954	BIOSAMPLE:SAMEA2733980

Identifiers for genomic tracks?

- Should there be globally unique, persistent identifiers for genomic track files (e.g. BigBED/BigWIG, VCF, etc)
- No such thing exists, but we highly recommend that they should be created and indexed
- Also, identifiers for *track collections* would be very useful
 - Would easily FAIRify "Mix-and-match" track file collections analysed in particular research papers, if the track files are already FAIRified

Updates

- ELIXIR Recommended Interoperability Resource 2021
- Manuscript published Apr 2021
- Invited blog post in F1000Research published Dec 2021
- New web site published 2022: <https://fairtracks.net>

FAIRtracks

– Hoards of genomic track data at your fingertips

In the spirit of Open Science, the FAIRtracks ecosystem provides technical solutions for the abundance of genome browser track files ("genomic tracks") to become "Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR)" in new research contexts.

COMMUNITY BUILDING

Bridging the data gaps

We aim to connect:

- data providers
- biocurators
- tool developers
- the FAIR community
- researchers/data analysts
- ...and other interested parties

Together we can mobilize the power of genomic tracks!

TECHNOLOGY

Quality metadata and services

Working in concert with the FAIRtracks draft standard for metadata of genomic tracks, we have built an ecosystem of services to interface with track metadata, including:

- Metadata augmentation
- Metadata validation
- Metadata transformation
- Precision search

You can connect to these core services both upstream (for data providers/biocurators) and downstream (for tool developers/analytical end users).

ORGANIZATIONAL BACKING

Endorsed by ELIXIR

The FAIRtracks ecosystem is developed and provided as part of the national Service Delivery Plans by ELIXIR Norway and ELIXIR Spain, and is supported by the Track Hub Registry group at EMBL-EBI.

FAIRtracks is endorsed by ELIXIR Europe as a Recommended Interoperability Resource (RIR).

But we need more partners:

Please help us bring the wealth of available track data and metadata to the fingertips of researchers and bioinformaticians everywhere!

Projects / collaborations

- Galaxy implementation study (2021-2023)
 - Task 1.4. Enhanced metadata functionality in Galaxy to support querying and importing of FAIRtracks-annotated genomic track data
 - Implement [TrackFind](#) client as a Galaxy tool
 - Idea: associate FAIRtracks metadata with data as a Galaxy dataset/collection, keeping this relation through downstream analysis steps
 - Investigate RO-Crate integration
- RDA TIGER (HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-01-04)
 - RDA/EOSC project started Jan 2023
 - Demonstrator Working Group for RDA TIGER (pre-approved, but still need to apply)
 - Goal is to integrate metadata from (at least) Functional Annotation of ANimal Genomes (FAANG) into FAIRtracks, and also expand tool interoperability
 - Some funding available
 - More importantly: door-opener into both RDA and EOSC

Literary digression: omnify

So that the Church of England, in these manners of dispensing the power of the keys, does cut off all disputings and impertinent wranglings, whether the priest's power were judicial or declarative; for possibly it is both, and it is optative too, and something else yet; for it is an emanation from all the parts of his ministry, and he never absolves, but he preaches or prays, or administers a sacrament; for this power of remission is a transcendent, passing through all the parts of the priestly offices. For the keys of the kingdom of heaven are the promises and the threatenings of the Scripture, and the prayers of the Church, and the Word, and the Sacraments, and all these are to be dispensed by the priest, and these keys are committed to his ministry, and by the operation of them all he opens and shuts heaven's gates ministerially.

No more ingenious way of making nothing of a thing than by making it every thing. **Omnify** the disputed point into a transcendent, and you may defy the opponent to lay hold of it. He might as well attempt to grasp an *aura electrica*.

"Notes on Jeremy Taylor",
The Literary Remains Of Samuel Taylor Coleridge,
by Samuel Taylor Coleridge
Publication date: 1836-1839

- One of the most obscure words in the English language:

omnify transitive verb

om·ni·fy 'äm·nə·fī

-ed/-ing/-es

: to make universal : **ENLARGE**

**Rerunnable
metadata
transformation
workflows?**

uniFAIR

metadata

- Encode
- blueprint
- TCGA

Transform
How?

FAIRtracks standards
compliant Metadata

Encode

Normalized
(non-redundant)
Encode
tables

ENCODE
Model
map

Ontology
mapping /
conversion

Raw
FAIRtracks-
mapped
tables

Data cleanup

FAIRtracks
Validation

Minimum
FAIRtracks-
compliant
ENCODE
tables

Optional ->

Augmented
humanly
readable
FAIRtracks
tables

TCGA

Normalized
(non-redundant)
TCGA
tables

TCGA
Model
map

(Collapsing variations in naming)

- Required manual
(OpenRefine?)

Data portals

Custom metadata schemas:

ENCODE
FAANG
TCGA
ICSC
IHEC
...

Metadata exchange standard

FAIRtracks

Data portals

Custom metadata schemas:

ENCODE
FAANG
TCGA
ICSC
IHEC
...

Metadata exchange standard

FAIRtracks

FAIRtracks
metadata
ETL workflows

ISA JSON to ENA XML conversion
(Biohackaton 2022 project)

Data portals

Custom metadata schemas:

- ENCODE
- FAANG
- TCGA
- ICSC
- IHEC
- ...

Any data model

ISA-JSON

Metadata exchange standard

FAIRtracks

Any data model

ENA XML

Any data/metadata transformation workflow

Reusable metadata ETL modules

Extract

Transform

Load

Parse, don't validate!

- Alexis King: "Parse, don't validate" (2019 blog post)
 - Blog: <https://lexi-lambda.github.io/blog/2019/11/05/parse-don-t-validate/>
- Step-wise parsers munge the data to conform to schema/data model restrictions
- Allow for some variation in data input, with automatic type conversion
- Gradually improve structure of data

PREFECT v 2.0 - Orion

- Python-based dynamic orchestration engine
- Fully Open Source: *Apache 2.0 license*
- Dynamically registered, DAG-free workflows:
 - Supports *if/for/while* statements
 - Dynamic branching logic depending on runtime conditions
- Code as workflows:
 - No need to specify task and workflow parameters outside of normal code
 - Debug locally, run remotely using the same source code
 - Use tools you might already know, including:
 - Pydantic, FastAPI, RRule, Sqlite, asyncio, Dask, ...
- Rules engine:
 - State-based orchestration engine, with API separation
 - GUI Dashboard to administrer workflow runs
- A bunch of pre-built integrations:
 - data sources/destinations (*GitHub, PostgreSQL, Jupyter notebooks, etc.*)
 - deployment options (*Docker, Kubernetes, cloud storage, etc.*)

Simple Prefect workflow with two tasks
(from <https://orion-docs.prefect.io/tutorials/first-steps/#run-a-basic-flow-with-tasks>)

```
import requests
from prefect import flow, task

@task
def call_api(url):
    response = requests.get(url)
    print(response.status_code)
    return response.json()

@task
def parse_fact(response):
    print(response["fact"])
    return

@flow
def api_flow(url):
    fact_json = call_api(url)
    parse_fact(fact_json)
    return
```


Develop, inspect and deploy directly from IDE

The screenshot displays the PyCharm IDE interface. The main editor shows a CSV file named 'my_table.csv' with the following data:

	synonym	category	name	primaryAccession	uniProtkbId
1	CDC7L1	Technical term	3D-structure	000311	CDC7_HUMAN
2	CDC7L1	Coding sequence diversity	Alternative splicing	000311	CDC7_HUMAN
3	CDC7L1	Ligand	ATP-binding	000311	CDC7_HUMAN
4	CDC7L1	Biological process	Cell cycle	000311	CDC7_HUMAN
5	CDC7L1	Biological process	Cell division	000311	CDC7_HUMAN
6	CDC7L1	PTM	Isopeptide bond	000311	CDC7_HUMAN
7	CDC7L1	Molecular function	Kinase	000311	CDC7_HUMAN
8	CDC7L1	Ligand	Magnesium	000311	CDC7_HUMAN
9	CDC7L1	Ligand	Metal-binding	000311	CDC7_HUMAN
10	CDC7L1	Ligand	Nucleotide-binding	000311	CDC7_HUMAN
11	CDC7L1	Cellular component	Nucleus	000311	CDC7_HUMAN
12	CDC7L1	PTM	Phosphoprotein	000311	CDC7_HUMAN
13	CDC7L1	Technical term	Reference proteome	000311	CDC7_HUMAN
14	CDC7L1	Molecular function	Serine/threonine-protein kinase	000311	CDC7_HUMAN
15	CDC7L1	Molecular function	Transferase	000311	CDC7_HUMAN
16	CDC7L1	PTM	Ubl conjugation	000311	CDC7_HUMAN
17	Cdc7l1	Coding sequence diversity	Alternative splicing	Q9Z0H0	CDC7_MOUSE
18	Cdc7l1	Ligand	ATP-binding	Q9Z0H0	CDC7_MOUSE
19	Cdc7l1	Biological process	Cell cycle	Q9Z0H0	CDC7_MOUSE

The terminal window at the bottom shows the following logs:

```
[OMNIPY] Mon Feb 27 13:52:44 2023 - INFO: Finished running "linear-flow-import-and-flatten-uniprot-scrupulous-snake"! [omnipy.log.registry.RunStateRegistry]
[OMNIPY] Mon Feb 27 13:52:44 2023 - INFO: Writing dataset as a gzipped tarpack to "/Users/sveinugu/PycharmProjects/omnipy_examples/data/2023_02_27-13_52_44/04_line
[OMNIPY] Mon Feb 27 13:52:44 2023 - INFO: Initialized "task-pandas-magic-qualified-zebra" [omnipy.log.registry.RunStateRegistry]
[OMNIPY] Mon Feb 27 13:52:44 2023 - INFO: Started running "task-pandas-magic-qualified-zebra" ... [omnipy.log.registry.RunStateRegistry]
[OMNIPY] Mon Feb 27 13:52:44 2023 - INFO: Finished running "task-pandas-magic-qualified-zebra"! [omnipy.log.registry.RunStateRegistry]
[OMNIPY] Mon Feb 27 13:52:44 2023 - INFO: Writing dataset as a gzipped tarpack to "/Users/sveinugu/PycharmProjects/omnipy_examples/data/2023_02_27-13_52_44/05_task
[OMNIPY] Mon Feb 27 13:52:44 2023 - INFO: Finished running "func-flow-import-and-flatten-uniprot-with-magic-uppish-pudu"! [omnipy.log.registry.RunStateRegistry]
[OMNIPY] Mon Feb 27 13:52:44 2023 - INFO: Writing dataset as a gzipped tarpack to "/Users/sveinugu/PycharmProjects/omnipy_examples/data/2023_02_27-13_52_44/06_func

Process finished with exit code 0
```

The IDE interface includes a project structure on the left, a top toolbar with various icons, and a bottom status bar showing 'Sourcery <no default server> omnipy_examples master 0/up-to-date 627 of 2048M'.

Prefect orchestration GUI for local and remote deployment

The screenshot displays the Prefect orchestration GUI's 'Blocks / Choose a Block' interface. On the left is a dark sidebar with navigation options: Flow Runs, Flows, Deployments, Work Queues, Blocks (highlighted), Notifications, and Settings. The main content area shows a grid of 12 blocks, each with a logo, name, description, capabilities, and an 'Add +' button. At the top right of the grid is a search bar and a 'Capability: all' dropdown.

Block Name	Description	Capabilities
Azure	Store data as a file on Azure Datalake and Azure Blob Storage.	get-directory, put-directory, read-path, write-path
Date Time	A block that represents a datetime	
Docker Container	Runs a command in a container. Requires a Docker Engine to be connectable. Docker settings will be retrieved from the environment.	run-infrastructure
Docker Registry	Connects to a Docker registry. Requires a Docker Engine to be connectable. Login information is persisted to disk at the Docker default location.	docker-login
GCS	Store data as a file on Google Cloud Storage.	get-directory, put-directory, read-path, write-path
GitHub	Interact with files stored on public GitHub repositories.	get-directory
JSON	A block that represents JSON	
Kubernetes Cluster Config	Stores configuration for interaction with Kubernetes clusters. See 'from_file' for creation.	
Kubernetes Job	Runs a command as a Kubernetes Job.	run-infrastructure
Local File System	Store data as a file on a local file system.	get-directory, put-directory, read-path, write-path
Microsoft Teams Webhook	Enables sending notifications via a provided Microsoft Teams webhook.	notify
Process	Run a command in a new process. Current environment variables and Prefect settings will be included in the created process. Configured environment variables will override any...	run-infrastructure

More information on Omnipy

Figure 7.1. The difference between making research (meta)data FAIR by Design from the outset and FAIRing Backwards. From Doble, Centre How are we Faring with FAIR? (and what FAIR is not). FAIR Data Infrastructures, 15 October 2020. License: CC BY 4.0

Transformation

Principles and novel toolset for FAIRification and 'data wrangling'

FAIR by design, FAIRification and Data brokering. There is a distinction between research data that has been made FAIR by design at the outset and research data that require a process of retroactive FAIRification (see Figure 7.1). In the FAIR-by-design case, metadata can be entered more or less directly according to the FAIR metadata schema, after which a validator can be applied to locate eventual errors. *Retrospective FAIRification* will, on the other hand, typically first require a process of transformation, cleaning, and mapping of the existing metadata from its previous shape into a new shape that follows a more FAIR-compliant schema. A similar process of metadata transformation and mapping happens in the process of *data brokering*, where metadata entered according to one metadata schema is automatically transformed to follow another schema and submitted to a data deposition service. In both cases, a validator will only be able to check the end result of a transformation process, it will not help much with the actual work of getting there.

“ In both cases, a validator will only be able to check the end result of a transformation process, it will not help much with the actual work of getting there ”

“Parse, don't validate”. A complementary approach to applying a validator at the end is to uphold the schema restrictions through a set of data parsers in the transformation process itself. In contrast to validators, parsers will typically allow a level of variation and noise in the input data, but still make sure that the output data follow the relevant restrictions. This alternative approach to *data wrangling* can be summed up in the concept “parse, don't validate”. See *Technical note #2* (to the side) for a more in-depth look at this concept.

Validators as the authority. Parsing-based approaches are powerful, but still, in our view, complementary to traditional validators. As one often needs to set up several transformation processes, there is still the need of a single validator to be the authoritative judge in case of disagreements. Also, as mentioned above, parsers are not applicable to all scenarios.

FAIRtracks
FAIRtracks is a secondary metadata standard: Genomic track files are most often created as secondary by-products derived from the raw experiment data (see e.g. *Finding Tracks*). Hence, the choice of primary metadata schemas are typically dictated by circumstances relating to the raw data, e.g. to follow schemas required by *research data management (RDM)* or *data deposition services*. For projects that are part of larger consortia undertakings, required metadata schemas are typically defined centrally (see *Track Collections*). In both cases, the *FAIRtracks standard* is a secondary metadata exchange standard that aims to facilitate interoperability and reuse of the data through a central indexing service and downstream software integrations (see *Finding Tracks*).

“ We are developing uniFAIR, a systematic and scalable approach to research data transformation and “wrangling” in Python ”

The importance of a good solution for metadata transformation: Being a secondary metadata standard, it is imperative for *community adoption* of FAIRtracks that we provide good solutions for transforming metadata from its primary form into the FAIRtracks standard. To this end, we are developing *uniFAIR*, a systematic and scalable approach to research data transformation and “wrangling” in Python.

uniFAIR
Generic functionality. uniFAIR is designed primarily to simplify development and deployment of (meta)data transformation processes in the context of FAIRification and data brokering efforts. However, the functionality is very generic and can also be used to support research data (and metadata) transformations in a range of fields and contexts beyond life science, including day-to-day research scenarios (see Figure 7.2).

Data wrangling in day-to-day research: Researchers in life science and other data-centric fields often need to extract, manipulate and integrate data and/or metadata from different sources, such as repositories, databases or flat files. Much research time is spent on trivial and not-so-trivial details of such “data wrangling”:

- reformat data structures
- clean up errors
- remove duplicate data
- map and integrate dataset fields
- etc.

General software for data wrangling and analysis, such as *Pandas*, *R* or *Friktionless*, are useful, but researchers still regularly end up with hard-to-reuse scripts, often with manual steps.

Step-wise data model transformations: With the *uniFAIR* Python package, researchers can import (meta)data in almost any shape or form: *nested JSON*, *tabular (relational) data*, *binary streams*, or other data structures. Through a step-by-step process, data is continuously parsed and reshaped according to a series of data model transformations.

“ uniFAIR tasks (single steps) and flows (workflows) are ”

- Check out the newly launched redesign of the FAIRtracks website:

- <https://fairtracks.net>

- Specifically:

- <https://fairtracks.net/fair/#fair-07-transformation>

- GitHub repo:

- <https://github.com/fairtracks/omnipy>

TECH NOTE #2. PARSE, DON'T VALIDATE

TYPE-DRIVEN DESIGN
This alternative approach to *data wrangling* is summed up in a slogan coined by Alexis King in 2019 in an influential blog post: “*Parse, don't validate*”. King here argues for the use of “*type-driven design*”, also called “*type-driven development*”:

“ TYPE-DRIVEN DEVELOPMENT IS A STYLE OF PROGRAMMING IN WHICH WE WRITE TYPES FIRST AND USE THOSE TYPES TO GUIDE THE DEFINITION OF FUNCTIONS. ”

Brady E. *Type-driven development with Java*. Smart and Schuster, 2017.

This definition of “*type-driven development*” entails that each parser is defined at the outset to guarantee the production of a particular data type (also called “*data model*”, “*data structure*” or “*schema*”). With an abundance of different precisely defined data types in the code base, transformations can be defined with precise syntax as a cascade of data type conversions, e.g.

```
let [ Any ] > list [ str ] > list [ count ( ge = 0, le = 1000 ) ]
```

* These data types were written using Python type hint notation, where `count(ge=0, le=1000)` is a *pydantic* data type representing a positive integer less than or equal to 1000.

THE DATA TYPES REMEMBER
A main advantage of this approach is that once a variable is defined to follow a particular data type, e.g. “*list of positive integers less than or equal to 1000*”, then this restriction is preserved in the data type itself; the variable never needs to be parsed or validated again.

REQUIRES STATIC TYPING
The “*Parse, don't validate*” approach requires that the programming language is *statically typed* and also that the language supports complex data types, so that e.g. a full metadata schema can be expressed as a type. It is no surprise that Alexis King in the above mentioned blog post demonstrated the concepts in *Haskell*, a statically typed and *purely functional* programming language.

WHAT ABOUT PYTHON?
Python is one of the most popular programming languages in bioinformatics and data science in general. Python is also one of the most famous examples of a *duck typed* language, i.e. “*that if something “walks like a duck and quacks like a duck, then it must be a duck*”. Unfortunately, in traditional Python code, if a variable looks like a “*list of positive integers less than 1000*”, there is no way to know this for sure without validating the full list, and even then, there are no guarantees that the data will stay that way forever.

Fortunately, with the integration of *type hints* and compile-time static type checkers such as *mypy* this is changing. Moreover, with the advent of run-

Collaboration

We have limited development resources and are aiming for FAIRtracks to become a community endeavor!

We are planning a BioHackathon project on expanding to Omnipy and are looking for collaborators, e.g. to integrate other resources or standards into Omnipy or to use Omnipy to set up metadata transformation.

We are interested in any types of contributions & collaborations!

Please contact us at: fairtracks@elixir.no

Acknowledgements

FAIRtracks

S. Gundersen and the FAIRtracks team:

EBI/EMBL, Hinxton, UK

+

**ELIXIR Norway,
Centre of Bioinformatics, UiO**

**ELIXIR Spain,
Barcelona Supercomputing Centre**

**ELIXIR Norway,
NTNU & UiB**

+

+

**Jeanne Cheneby,
Pável Vázquez**

Acknowledgements

**Metabolomics Community & Interoperability
Platform - on which subjects could they
collaborate?**

Metabolomics Community & Interoperability Platform

On which subjects could they collaborate?

Maria I. Klapa, ELIXIR-GR (FORTH)
mklapa@iceht.forth.gr

www.elixir-europe.org

The ELIXIR Metabolomics Community

... works with experimental scientists, computational scientists and (metabolomics technology) developers to provide the resources, analysis tools and infrastructures that will enable metabolomics research.

The community will also establish an infrastructure of services, standards and datasets to help researchers discover, annotate and analyse metabolomics data from around Europe and integrate these with other data sources in an OMICS setting.

... Established back in 2018

F1000Research F1000Research 2017, 6(ELIXIR):1649 Last updated: 10 OCT 2019

OPINION ARTICLE
REVISED The future of metabolomics in ELIXIR [version 2; peer review: 3 approved]

Merlijn van Rijswijk ³, Christophe Caron⁴, Marta Cascante⁵,
Victoria Dominguez ⁴, Warwick B. Dunn⁶, Timothy M. D. Ebbels⁷,
Franck Giacomoni⁸, Alejandra Gonzalez-Beltran ⁹, Thomas Hankemeier^{2,10},
Kenneth Haug ¹⁴,
Fabien Jourdan¹⁵, Namrata Kale ¹⁷⁻¹⁹,

... and Lipidomics!

... and Fluxomics!

Goals of the Community

- **To create and extend metabolomics datasets**
 - Work with ELIXIR-recommended deposition service: EMBL-EBI [Metabolights](#)
- **To develop data analysis workflows for metabolomics**
 - Work with workflow management e-infrastructures such as [Workflow4Metabolomics](#), [PhenoMeNal](#), and [Galaxy-M](#)
- **To promote data standards and interoperability in metabolomics**
 - Promote [FAIR principles](#), develop the [ISA framework](#) as a basis for metadata standards and to agree on persistent identifiers for metabolites, using tools like [SPLASH](#).
- **To support computing with large-scale metabolomics data**
- **To increase the metabolomics training available**

Leadership

2018

**Christoph
Steinbeck**
(ELIXIR
DE)

**Thomas
Hankemeier**
(ELIXIR NL)

**Claire
O'Donovan**
(EMBL-EBI)

**Merlijn Van
Rijswijk**
(ELIXIR NL)

John Hancock
Communities
Coordinator
(ELIXIR Hub)

2022

**Steffen
Neumann**
(ELIXIR-DE)

**Claire
O'Donovan**
(EMBL-EBI)

**Maria
Klapa**
(ELIXIR-GR)

**Katharina
Heil**
(ELIXIR Hub)

MetaboLights

Open Source Study Repository & Metabolite Knowledgebase

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights>

- Cross species, cross technique
- Comprehensive information collection
- Open access, discoverable through various portals

Our Implementation studies

MetID Implementation Study

- **Metabolite identification** is main bottleneck in metabolomics:
 - Crucial for data analysis & biological interpretation
 - Crucial for personalized medicine and prevention, crop improvement, industrial biotechnology and environmental research
- Metabolite identification requires **standardization**, **computational** metabolomics & metabolomics **data** management
- Hence the **Implementation Study**
- Objectives are:
 - Identification **pipeline integrating tools** for metabolite identification
 - Metabolite identification database incl. MS spectra, metadata and quality assignment

See the [presentation](#) @ AllHands 2020 for all the gory details

Metabolic Model Standardization

Significance

A major need in multi-omic data integration & in fluxomic analysis

Can we go directly from the proteomic to the metabolomic profile?

Schematic of interconnectivity between major molecular classes & processes in a cell :
The role of metabolism – metabolic reactome

Schematic of interconnectivity between major molecular classes & processes in a cell :
The role of metabolism – metabolic reactome

Needs that lead to the IS for Standardizing the fluxomics workflows (Jun 2019 – Nov 2021)

- **Standardization of the isotopic tracer data deposition and development of a standardized repository** to enable combined studies and meta-analyses
- **Develop a collection of the largely used fluxomics tools - Interoperability between the fluxomics tools** and with the metabolomic/isotopomic & metabolic reaction databases
- Standardized *extended* metabolic reaction databases enabling linking metabolomic and fluxomic analyses to other omic data
- Standardized metabolic network reconstruction workflows - models
- **Standardized fluxomics training** (portals, workshops, summer courses) – diversity of disciplines involved

“Relational Scheme” of the Fluxomics IS

Interoperability-Related Activities

Deliverable I1: Extended PhenoMeNal flux software to LC-MS and NMR isotopic data & appropriately adapt Isodyn software (lead: ELIXIR-ES).

Deliverable I2:

- (a) Consolidated workflow outputs towards standard compliant files (SBML, JSON data packages), lead ELIXIR-UK (UOXF);
- (b) Extended OpenMS to ^{13}C -fluxomics data, lead ELIXIR-DE (U Tübingen);
- (c) Added IsoCor and Influx_si to the workflow, lead ELIXIR-FR (INRA-MetaboHub);
- (d) Comparative testing of tools for large-scale ^{13}C -based flux analysis; adding tool for atomically resolve a metabolic reconstruction, lead ELIXIR-NL (UL)

Deliverable I3:

- (a) Extended *BridgeDb resource* for reaction identifier mapping into fluxomics (lead: Interoperability platform located at ELIXIR-NL, C. Evelo//E. Willighagen, Umas)

Towards the Development of a Framework for Multi-omic Data Analysis

PICKLE: A meta-database of Human Protein-Protein Interactions
<http://www.pickle.gr/>

MetaboLights
<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights/>

Standardized Repositories of Metabolomic Data

Challenges in Genome-Scale Metabolic Network Reconstruction

Gap Filling based:

1. Experimental Data (Metabolomic/Transcriptomic)
2. Biochemistry – Stoichiometric Information
3. Information about Enzymatic Function

Cellular Compartmentalization?

Source & Sink Reactions for ATP & Cofactors?

Tissue Specificity ?

Transport Reactions (Dead Ends) ?

Issues with the non-standardization of human metabolic models

One Model in Many Repositories

One model in many formats, not necessarily the same in all repositories

Model Repositories

VIRTUAL METABOLIC HUMAN <https://www.vmh.life/#home>
Noronha et al., 2019 - Recon series

BiGG Models <http://bigg.ucsd.edu/>
King et al., 2016

metabolic ATLAS <https://metabolicatlas.org>
Robinson et al., 2020 - HMR series

BioModels <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biomodels/> - EBI
Glont et al., 2018; Malik-Sheriff et al., 2020

MetaNetX <https://www.metanetx.org/cgi-bin/mnxweb/repository> - SIB
Moretti et al., 2020

Metabolic Databases

Rhea <https://www.rhea-db.org/>
Alcántara et al., 2012

HUMANCYC <https://humancyc.org/>
Karp and Caspi, 2011

reactome <https://reactome.org/>
Gillespie et al., 2022

KEGG <https://www.genome.jp/kegg/>
Kanehisa et al., 2019

Multiple Stoichiometric Models →

Need to standardize the reconstruction process

- Multiple generic & tissue-specific metabolic models for human
- Available through many repositories and in different formats
- Need to standardize the reconstruction, representation and storage of metabolic stoichiometric models
- Standardization will enable the educated selection of the most appropriate model for specific applications, and the direct comparison of fluxomic studies.
- Alignment of metabolic models with (human) genome and proteome will reveal which parts need reconsideration and/or updating and is important for multi-omic studies.
- Need for rules for the educated modification of a metabolic model to that/those of related species

What does MC need from the Interoperability platform ?

- Interoperability standards for metabolomic data deposition and analysis tools
- Interoperability standards for metabolic model repositories
- Interoperability standards for flux tools
- Interoperability between data, tools, models for consistent workflows for metabolomics, fluxomics and multi-omics
- Promote [FAIR principles](#) in metabolomic data deposition, fluxomic analysis tools, integration of metabolomics with other omics

For questions and feedback please use:

mklapa@iceht.forth.gr

